

December 23, 2011

VIA ELECTRONIC FILING

Marlene H. Dortch
Secretary
Federal Communications Commission
445 12th Street, SW
Washington, DC 20554

Re: LightSquared Subsidiary LLC, *Ex Parte* Communication
IB Docket No. 11-109; IBFS File No. SAT-MOD-20101118-00239

Dear Ms. Dortch:

LightSquared Subsidiary LLC ("LightSquared") hereby submits the results and assessments of recent independent laboratory testing of enhanced high precision GPS equipment. Results from the testing of additional enhanced high precision devices are currently being compiled and will be submitted to the Commission in a subsequent filing.

If you have questions, please do not hesitate to contact me.

Sincerely,

/s/

Jeffrey J. Carlisle
Executive Vice President, Regulatory Affairs
and Public Policy
703-390-2001

Attachments

cc: IB-SATFO@fcc.gov

Summary and Assessment of Results of Independent Testing of Upgraded High Precision Devices (Group 1)

Prepared by LightSquared, December 23, 2011

Background

On June 30, 2011, concurrent with the release of the final report of the Technical Working Group (TWG) formed to study the GPS overload issue, LightSquared committed to work cooperatively with the GPS community to develop solutions for high precision receivers so that all could be made fully resilient to LightSquared's adjacent-band operations.

It was clear from the outset that this was a task that could be accomplished quickly and with currently-available components and technology – as evidenced by the fact that many high precision devices tested by the TWG already demonstrated necessary levels of resiliency. LightSquared immediately began assisting filter and equipment manufacturers in the specification of components leading to the production of devices that demonstrated that existing models could be quickly upgraded to properly reject LightSquared's adjacent-band signal.

Work continued through the summer and by early fall, the first such devices were announced by leading equipment manufacturers. In order to fully demonstrate the resiliency and capabilities of these devices, LightSquared contracted with Alcatel Lucent Bell Labs (ALU) to perform independent laboratory testing.

LightSquared directly purchased a variety of legacy high precision GPS devices on the open market and invited all major manufacturers to participate in the testing program, many of which availed themselves of the opportunity to test newly modified devices and antennas. Where manufacturers did not elect to participate in the testing process, LightSquared paired legacy devices with modified external antennas submitted by participating manufacturers in order to assess their resiliency and performance. These results demonstrated that legacy devices (that utilize external antennas) could be paired with antennas from other manufacturers and achieve the necessary levels of resiliency while maintaining the same performance specifications.

Attachment 1 is the ALU test report providing data from the test of devices from Javad GNSS and TOPCON, which were the first devices to be tested. Attachment 2 is a test report from Hemisphere GPS which details the results of their device testing at the ALU facility. Attachment 3 is a test report from a manufacturer who does not wish to identify itself publicly and is referred to herein as "Manufacturer 1" and details the result of the testing of its devices at the ALU facility. Information regarding the identity of the devices tested by Manufacturer 1 will be submitted to the FCC with a request for confidential treatment.

This filing constitutes the first group of reports assembled by ALU and equipment manufacturers, but does not represent the full range of testing performed at ALU. Reports from testing of additional devices from other manufacturers will be submitted as they become available.

Test Process

Testing at an ALU anechoic test chamber in Murray Hill, NJ began on November 21, 2011 with the testing concluding for the devices included in this report by December 14, 2011. The details of the test plan, which are consistent with the industry best practices for high precision device testing established by the TWG, are detailed in Attachment 4. The test plan was also sent to several GPS manufacturers whose suggested edits were incorporated into the document.

The anechoic chamber was set up and calibrated by ALU, with some manufacturers conducting testing of their own devices under the observation of ALU and LightSquared; other legacy devices were tested by ALU (paired with upgraded antennas provided by other manufacturers) without the legacy device manufacturer participating in the testing process. All testing was performed against LightSquared's lower 10 MHz downlink channel (1526-1536 MHz) as well as uplink channels (1637.5-1647.5 MHz and 1646.7-1656.7 MHz)

Test Results

The test results demonstrate conclusively that high precision receivers can be made fully resilient to LightSquared's adjacent band transmissions while maintaining all of their necessary performance specifications. In the Hemisphere report, it is demonstrated that the enhanced Hemisphere and Javad antennas provide location accuracy at least equal to that of the unmodified legacy Hemisphere external antenna when paired with a legacy device. Similar results are presented by Manufacturer 1 in its test report. These assessments were also confirmed by an analysis LightSquared performed on position information collected by ALU on the Javad and Topcon devices during the testing process. Copies of the raw data files compiled during the testing process are available from ALU.

Below, LightSquared presents select graphs from the ALU and manufacturer reports that demonstrate the resiliency of the solutions tested. The full ALU and manufacturer assessments are contained in their attached reports.

ALU and manufacturer assessments of device tracking performance (L1) in presence of LightSquared Lower 10 MHz (downlink) signal

Note: Eclipse II receivers and A52 antennas are Hemisphere GPS products

Results from Manufacturer 1

The above graphs demonstrate that the combinations of high precision receivers and antennas tested in the ALU facility are fully resilient to LightSquared's Lower 10 MHz (downlink) channel operations at any power levels which would be experienced on the ground.

ALU and manufacturer assessments of device tracking performance (L1) in presence of LightSquared uplink signal(s)

Graphs for Javad and Topcon devices are for the combined uplink signals centered on 1632.5 MHz and 1651.7 MHz

The graph below represents the test results produced by Hemisphere GPS for the LightSquared uplink channel centered on 1632.5 MHz

Results from Manufacturer 1 (graphs below are for the combined uplink signals centered on 1632.5 MHz and 1651.7 MHz)

The above results demonstrate that there is no degradation experienced by devices paired with upgraded external antennas when exposed to LightSquared uplink signals at power levels which would be experienced during operation.

ALU and manufacturer assessments of device tracking performance in presence of LightSquared uplink and downlink signals

The Javad graph was not available at time of filing; it will be submitted in a subsequent filing.

Results from testing of Hemisphere legacy device with upgraded antennas

Results from Manufacturer 1 (Reporting L1 and L2 results)

Finally, the above tests demonstrate that devices are resilient to the combination of LightSquared downlink and uplink transmissions when outfitted with upgraded external antennas. It should also be noted that the uplink signal used during the test is worst-case, since the LightSquared system utilizes uplink power control. Thus, if the handset is near a LightSquared base station, the power of the handset will be limited by the power control function of the network and will be much less than what was used in the test. Therefore, it will not be additive to the LightSquared downlink signal to the degree it was simulated in the testing at ALU, which results in an extra layer of margin for GPS devices.

Conclusion

As demonstrated by the test results attached to this filing, LightSquared’s planned terrestrial deployment is fully compatible with GPS operation, even for the highest precision equipment available on the commercial market. Leading manufacturers have quickly demonstrated that resiliency can be achieved using readily available components which have similar costs and form factors to those that have previously been used by the equipment. Significant additional testing has been conducted at the ALU facility, producing similar results to those included herein. ALU and participating equipment manufacturers are in the process of assembling these results as well and these will be submitted to the Commission shortly.

LightSquared commends the high precision equipment manufacturers who have quickly come forward and produced devices and tested these solutions. By doing so, they are demonstrating their commitment not only to responsible spectrum management practices, but to continued innovation and development. This will allow their customers to continue to utilize highly accurate GPS services while at the same time benefitting, as will all consumers, from the wireless broadband services to be offered by LightSquared.